

AN EFFECTIVE WAY TO TEACH ENGLISH TO STUDENTS.

Raxmatullayev Orif Qurbanovich

Samarqand viloyati Urgut tumani
17-maktab ingliz tili o'qituvchisi
rahmatullayevorif@gmail.com
+998990959531

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10052425>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 25-October 2023 yil
Ma'qullandi: 28- October 2023 yil
Nashr qilindi: 30- October 2023 yil

KEY WORDS

innovative technologies, Power Point, Word, quality level, traditional methods, picture and video lessons, language, English language learning, educational technologies, project, interest, activity, interactive methods.

ABSTRACT

this article discusses the effective methods of teaching English to students, the use of innovative technologies in the process of language learning and teaching, and the improvement of efficiency through these methods.

Educating children who are fully mature, have high potential, are loyal to the ideas of national independence, and at the same time, who have thoroughly mastered modern knowledge, computer technology, and know a foreign language perfectly is one of the requirements of the current era. After all, today's youth are our tomorrow. In this regard, today's teachers are required to have a great responsibility, it is a very difficult task to surprise or interest students in this rapidly developing period. Methodological training of English language teachers is especially important. In addition to having a good knowledge of science, only a teacher who widely uses the possibilities of information technologies, which are widely introduced in education today, can achieve high results during his work. A modern teacher, along with deep knowledge of his subject, should be aware of advanced pedagogical and information communication technologies, be able to use the Internet and computer capabilities at a high level. For this, of course, in order to make each lesson interesting, the lively and interesting organization through multimedia tools, didactic materials, and visual aids serves the effectiveness of education. In fact, the practical study of a foreign language means the development of oral speech. As it was determined, the basis of the English language science is manifested in the formation of speech activity skills in students. It is known that speech activity can be both written and oral. It cannot be said that only mastering oral speech is practical knowledge. The process of practical acquisition is characterized by the acquisition of all types of speech activity. A student learning a foreign language should be able to convey his thoughts clearly and fully understand

the meanings. Studying the geography, literature, and history of the country where the language is being studied will also motivate you to master the language more perfectly. In this place, the lesson conducted using multimedia tools is of great importance. In addition to this, it should be noted that high results are achieved when using modern educational methods during the lesson. For example, brainstorming and group work have a big impact on work style. Learners discuss the topic in every way and express critical opinions, which in turn helps to develop the ability of a person to ask questions, speak, think logically, and develop the culture of discussion. Working in a group helps the student to develop the ability to work in a group, critical and independent thinking, communication and cooperation. Through the method of group work, he will have the opportunity to think at a high level, master the topic thoroughly, establish positive and friendly relations among group members, and self-management. It is worth noting that the role of lexis in learning English is more important than that of grammar. It is the lexicon that expresses the idea directly. Lexicon, that is, it allows you to imagine a word. According to experts, the fact that there are more than 500,000 words in the English language today shows that a student should constantly increase his vocabulary. For this purpose, the listening of oral texts (Listening), the organization of dialogues and conversations between students (Speaking) helps to make English lessons meaningful and effective. In conclusion, it can be said that the organization of education based on modern innovative technologies is the main tool for achieving educational efficiency. Based on this, the organization of education on the basis of modern innovative technologies means the specific conditions for achieving the requirements and goals of modern education and the result of pedagogical processes aimed at improving the individual's independent creative activity. This effectively affects the development of speech activity and independent thinking in the student. Teaching foreign languages on the basis of innovative technologies greatly helps students in the formation of their professional activities. Students can learn foreign languages, including English, German, and French, closely related to their majors, through various programs such as TOEFL, IELTS, English for all, and Internet connection. Learning foreign languages through the Internet allows people who communicate in different languages to get in touch with each other, as well as to get to know countries and people's lifestyles. In this case, communicating with a person of the country whose language is being studied will help the student to express his or her thoughts in a foreign language, to correct his mistakes, and to learn new nouns.

Popular methods of teaching and learning English and Internet resources were used in the research process. During the writing of the article, the principles of theoretical deductive conclusion, analysis and synthesis, logicity were used. Teaching and learning a foreign language using modern technologies is one of the most fruitful ways. In this process, among other things: - when using computers, the student can watch and listen to foreign language videos, demonstrations, dialogues, movies or cartoons; - it is possible to listen and watch foreign language radio broadcasts and television programs; - use of tape recorders and cassettes, which are considered a more traditional method; - CD players can be used. The use of these technical tools makes the process of learning a foreign language more interesting and effective for students. We know that in the current educational process, the student should be the subject. Focusing more on interactive methods will increase the effectiveness of education. One of the most important requirements for English language classes is to teach

students to think independently. Today, English language teachers are using the following innovative methods based on the experience of pedagogues in the United States of America and England: - "Creative Problem Solving" to use this method, the beginning of the story is read and how it ends. the judgment of students is referred to; - "Merry Riddles" teaching riddles to students is important in teaching English, they learn unfamiliar words and find the answer to riddles; - "Quick answers" helps to increase the efficiency of the lesson; - "Chigil yozdi" ("Warm-up exercises") use of various games in the classroom to interest students in the lesson [3]; - "Pantomime" (pantomime) this method can be used in a lesson where very difficult topics need to be explained or when written exercises are performed and students are tired; - "A chain story" method helps students to develop oral speech; - "Acting characters" method can be used in all types of lessons. In order to teach the profession, people in professions such as "Interpreter", "Translator", "Writer", "Poet" can participate in the class and talk with students; - "Thinkers meeting" poets and writers such as U. Shakespeare, A. Navoi, R. Burns can be "invited". At such a time, using the wise words they said in the lesson will help young people to be educated as perfect people; - The "When pictures speak" method is very convenient and helps to teach English and develop the oral speech of students, for this, it is necessary to use pictures related to the topic; - Quiz cards are distributed according to the number of students and allow all students to participate in the lesson at the same time, which saves time [4]. As we have seen, each innovative technology has its own advantages. In all such methods, cooperation between the teacher and the student, the active action of the student in the educational process is envisaged.

In our republic, new methods and requirements have been developed in accordance with the European Framework of Reference for Teaching Foreign Languages and Evaluating Knowledge and Skills of Foreign Language Teachers (CEFR). According to it, textbooks were created for students of general education schools and vocational colleges. In accordance with these requirements, classrooms were equipped with stands and new information and communication techniques. The demand for learning a foreign language is increasing day by day. Foreign language science is divided into four aspects (reading, speaking, listening comprehension and speaking), and separate concepts and skills are given for each of them. Educational technologies are effective use of modern information technologies in the educational process. It is also intended to increase the quality and efficiency of education by introducing modern innovative technologies into the educational process. In particular, there are several advantages of using such information and communication technologies in learning a foreign language. The role of modern technology in language learning and teaching is incomparable. The use of technological tools is useful in every aspect of learning a foreign language (reading, reading, listening and speaking). For example, in order to listen and understand, of course, this process cannot be carried out without a computer, player, CD discs. Listening comprehension is one of the most important parts of language learning. At the same time, the reader is required to pay attention to the speaker's pronunciation, adherence to grammatical rules, vocabulary and its meanings. An important factor in the use of modern technologies in the educational process is that students know information and communication technologies well and are able to use them. Teaching and learning a foreign language using modern technologies is one of the most fruitful ways.

In this process, including:

- when using computers, the student can watch and listen to foreign language videos, demonstrations, dialogues, movies or cartoons;
- it is possible to listen and watch foreign language radio broadcasts and television programs;
- use of tape recorders and cassettes, which are considered a more traditional method;
- CD players can be used. The use of these technical tools makes the process of learning a foreign language more interesting and effective for students. Today, teaching through interactive games is becoming a tradition in schools. It is known that the lesson is conducted on the basis of various games, which ensures that students demonstrate their capabilities, concentrate, improve their knowledge and skills, and become stronger. The basis of the use of game technology is the activity that activates and accelerates the student. According to psychologists, the psychological mechanisms of playful activity rely on the fundamental needs of a person to express himself, find a stable place in life, self-control, and realize his potential. Any game should be based on generally accepted educational principles and tactics. Educational games should be based on educational subjects. In the process of games, the student is more interested in this activity than in a regular lesson and works freely. It should be noted that the game is, first of all, a method of teaching. Pupils participate in game lessons with interest, strive to win, and the teacher also provides education to the pupil through them. The student believes that he can speak, listen, understand, and write in English while playing games, he is interested. We know that in the current educational process, the student should be the subject. Focusing more on interactive methods will increase the effectiveness of education. One of the most important requirements for English language classes is to teach students to think independently. Today, English language teachers are using the following innovative methods based on the experience of pedagogues in the United States of America and England: - "Creative Problem Solving" to use this method, the beginning of the story is read and how it ends. the judgment of students is referred to; - "Merry Riddles" teaching riddles to students is important in teaching English, they learn unfamiliar words and find the answer to riddles; - "Quick answers" helps to increase the efficiency of the lesson; - "Chigil yozdi" ("Warm-up exercises") use of various games in the classroom to interest students in the lesson [3]; - "Pantomime" (pantomime) this method can be used in a lesson where very difficult topics need to be explained or when written exercises are performed and students are tired; - "A chain story" method helps students to develop oral speech; - "Acting characters" method can be used in all types of lessons. In order to teach the profession, people in professions such as "Interpreter", "Translator", "Writer", "Poet" can participate in the class and talk with students;
- "Thinkers meeting" poets and writers such as U. Shakespeare, A. Navoi, R. Burns can be "invited". At such a time, using the wise words they said in the lesson will help young people to be educated as perfect people;
- The "When pictures speak" method is very convenient and helps to teach English and develop the oral speech of students, for this, it is necessary to use pictures related to the topic;
- Quiz cards are distributed according to the number of students and allow all students to participate in the lesson at the same time, which saves time. As we have seen, each innovative technology has its own advantages. In all such methods, cooperation between the teacher and the student, the active action of the student in the educational process is envisaged. In short, as a result of using innovative methods in English language classes,

students' logical thinking skills develop, their speech becomes fluent, and the ability to give quick and correct answers is formed. Such methods make students eager for knowledge. The student tries to prepare thoroughly for the lessons. This makes students active subjects of the educational process. As the educational system sets itself the task of educating a free-thinking, well-rounded, mature person, in the future, we future teachers will contribute by developing ways to effectively use innovative technologies.

References:

1. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ingliz-tilini-o-rgatishning-samarali-usullari>
2. bestpublication.uz
3. <https://moluch.ru/archive/308/69404/>
4. Toshpo'latov , A. (2023). SHAXS PSIXODIAGNOSTIKASIDA PROYEKTIV METODIKALARDAN FOYDALANISH. Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры, 3(5 Part 2), 170–178. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/ejsspc/article/view/16154>
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8001510>

